

Design and development of a framework to analyze performance and neural correlates of surgical learning

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Abstract—Surgical training often lack objective performance metrics, relying instead on instructor’s subjective evaluations. With the advent of surgical simulators, quantitative performance data can be gathered. However, simulators often do not deliver real-time metrics but rather summarize the trainee’s behavior after the exercise. Physiological signals can improve the feedback on students’ performance. The goal of this study is to develop a framework to analyze physiological and behavioral data associated with surgical learning, and to define metrics to objectively evaluate surgical performance. We present a modular framework that allows for various training setups, such as physical or virtual laparoscopic trainers, or robotic-assisted surgical training, and different physical and physiological measurements, as movements and electroencephalography (EEG). The proposed system offers a broader perspective on surgical skill acquisition, allowing to track real-time cognitive and behavioral indices.

Index Terms—Surgical training, Surgical learning, physiological signals, Electroencephalography (EEG), Motion capture (MoCap)

I. INTRODUCTION

Surgical procedures are complex tasks conducted under challenging physical and psychological conditions. They require extensive training to develop different skills including, manual, procedural and soft skills [1]. With each surgical technique (i.e., open, laparoscopic, and robot-assisted surgery), the surgeon-patient interface changes introducing difficulties that require the adaptation of technical skills to these contexts [2]. A critical challenge in surgical education is the reliance on subjective evaluation methods, such as self-evaluation questionnaires or instructor observations, which may not accurately reflect a trainee’s skill progression [3]. The teaching framework impacts the outcome of the acquired knowledge in the trainee [4]. Within this framework, there is a need for objective, real-time performance metrics that can enhance personalized training, thus maximizing individual skill development [5], [6].

Physiological metrics, have been explored as complementary measures for evaluating surgical skills and results [7], [8], albeit not homogeneous, support the idea that physiological signals can outline surgical learning. For this reason, the goal of this study is to design and develop a modular framework to analyze performance and physiological correlates of surgical learning, with the ultimate goal to identify a set of metrics that describe and evaluate surgical ability and learning.

II. OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of this research work are (i) to investigate novel methods for evaluating surgical skills, and (ii) to define objective metrics associated with surgical learning. To achieve the objectives, we designed a framework that can collect simultaneously various behavioral and physiological measures such as movements, EEG, as well as additional measures (e.g., electromyography - EMG, or skin conductance) during surgical practice [9]. The system can be used in different contexts: laparoscopy training using either a physical or a virtual simulator; robot-assisted surgery, and can also integrate haptic feedback. With the proposed framework, it would be possible to investigate many aspects, such as manual dexterity, workload, stress, and other cognitive processes associated with surgical learning [10]. Moreover, it would be possible to compare the learning process and highlight physiological metrics that differ between two different simulation systems (e.g., physical versus virtual simulations).

III. SOLUTION

The framework consists of three interconnected blocks (Fig. 1) and features a modular architecture, allowing for flexible integration of different simulators and data acquisition systems.

A. Simulation

It supports different types of systems ranging from physical box trainers, up to laparoscopic or robot-assisted surgery hybrid or virtual simulators. These simulations require the users to move surgical tools while interacting with a virtual environment. Moreover, haptic devices such as the Geomagic Touch can be integrated (Fig. 1). Regarding the virtual simulation, we combined a platform which employs Unity3D graphic engine, collects real-time data from the game engine and the movement tracking system and sends synchronization signals to the physiological data collection systems. Performance data are saved for subsequent analysis.

B. Tracking

A motion tracking system collects hands movements during the simulation; namely, movements of the surgical tools handled by the surgeon. These data (i) are sent in real time to the virtual simulation, to control the virtual replica of the surgical devices; (ii) are used to compute performance metrics (e.g., path length, speed, smoothness); (iii) are stored for off-line analysis; (iv) can be used to synchronize the physiological signals recording systems (Fig. 1).

C. Physiological Sensors

The framework supports data collection and synchronization of different physiological signals, such as EEG or EMG; due to the modular structure of the framework, additional data (i.e, skin conductance, heart rate) can be collected. A critical aspect of this setup is the robust synchronization between the blocks to ensure an accurate alignment between the datasets. Indeed, a correct synchronization ensures the possibility to compute event-related analysis also in the case of high time resolution signals. Finally, all the synchronized data will be stored for off-line analysis (Fig. 1).

As a demonstration of this framework, we designed an application focused on laparoscopic surgery. The *Simulation* consists of progressively challenging levels where the user manipulates an elastic band around pegs to form different

shapes, either using a physical box trainer, or an equivalent virtual simulation developed with Unity3D (Figure 1). Briefly, movements performed using real surgical instruments are *tracked* using the MoCap system (OptiTrack, NaturalPoint, Corvallis, OR, USA) and correspond to movements of the virtual objects through a client-server communication. As we are interested in analyzing the neural correlates associated with laparoscopic learning, we integrated the system with a EEG data collection system (i.e., *Physiological sensors* block).

IV. CONCLUSION

This work presents a modular framework for evaluating surgical performance through the integration of physiological and behavioral data. The system supports physical and virtual simulators, and combines hand movements recordings with physiological data collection, thus providing a comprehensive dataset to assess motor skills and cognitive processes associated with surgical learning. The framework's flexibility allows for a range of surgical tasks and setups, making it adaptable to various training needs. This study represents the first step toward personalized and improved surgical training programs. Future work will: focus on validating the framework; expanding it with additional physiological metrics; define performance feedback and deliver it in real time.

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Fig. 1. Framework Architecture. It consist of 3 modules: *Tracking* manages the real time recording of the manipulated surgical instrument; *Simulation* includes the systems used for surgical training; *Physiological Sensors* managing all the data recordings.